

Discovering alfanar Group's DIGI-FIT Future

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3. Abbreviations (sorted alphabetically)

Abbreviation	Full Form
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AWS	Amazon Web Services
DRP	Disaster Recovery Plan
EPC	Engineering, Procurement, and Construction
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Gen Z	Generation Z: mid-to-late 1990s through the early 2010s
GRC	Governance, Risk, and Compliance
HR	Human Resources
IE4	Industry 4.0
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
JIT	Just-In-Time
MEP	Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing
ML	Machine Learning
NCA	National Cybersecurity Authority
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PDPL	Personal Data Protection Law
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal
R&D	Research and Development
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDAIA	Saudi Data and Artificial Intelligence Authority

4. Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive analysis and strategic recommendations for digital transformation at alfanar Group, a leading industrial manufacturer and implementer of electricity and renewable energy solutions with operations across more than twenty countries and a significant GCC and global presence. The report analyzes alfanar's industry-related digital trends and relevant challenges and details how to overcome their impacts and implications through the digital adoption with a focus on how to enhance the overall efficiency and streamline the operations while maintaining a digital organizational culture as a competitive advantage.

5. Introduction

This report outlines how alfanar can adapt cutting-edge technologies through an analysis of opportunities as well as challenges of applicable digital trends like AI, IoT, Cloud Computing, and Cybersecurity. The report addresses the impact of IE4 on alfanar's macro environment and suggests risk mitigations towards threats associated with these technologies while highlighting substantial insights to overcome industry operational challenges, enhance data management, and improve the alfanar's culture of excellence.

6. About alfanar Group

alfanar Group, headquartered in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, is considered as one of globally-expanding companies in the field of manufacturing electrical construction products (switches and sockets, wires and cables, circuit breakers, electricity panels, and transformers) and the execution of construction, EPC and MEP solutions for both conventional and renewable power plants. This 40-year-old multi-national company employs over 35,000 individuals and caters to a diverse range of electrical, sustainable energy, engineering, and infrastructure industries across the global market. The Group started its transformation journey in 2018 prioritizing the digitizable aspects of its manufacturing operation and shared services through a strategy that leverages R&D, design thinking, and innovative environment.

Yet, alfanar is constantly striving, like all other mid-size globally-operating companies, to maximize the utilization of IE4 technologies and keep the digital-related risks under control.

7. Analysis of Mega Trends

According to McKinsey & Company (Anon., 2024), there are fifteen global technology trends nowadays. Three of them: AI, advanced connectivity and cloud computing are being heavily adapted by alfanar (Figure 1). This is in addition to cybersecurity which is a crucial enabler aspect of digital transformation.

Figure 1: Top 15 technology trends
Source: McKinsey & Company - 2023

7.1. AI Analysis

Companies investing in AI and ML have achieved 6% to 12% three-year returns higher than market averages (Sinderman, et al., 2023). Such a cutting-edge technology helps 23% of managers (Figure 2) in achieving higher quality results.

Figure 2: Percent of managers using Gen AI Tools
Source: McKinsey&Company

AI is expected to add a value of \$4.4 trillion annually to the global economy (Anon., 2024). Manufacturers can utilize AI and ML, in functions like maintenance, supply chain, employee self-services similar to companies achieved 40% of FTE savings (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percent of Gen AI Effect on FTE per business function
Source: McKinsey&Company

7.2. IoT Analysis

IoT market recorded a volume of \$ 595 billion in 2023 (Anon., 2024). It is growing towards \$1,4 trillion in 2024 although it is still too expensive (Yadoshchuk, 2024). IoT technology can significantly strengthen manufacturing sector by providing real-time monitoring and data collection for manufacturing processes and project sites (Rood, 2024).

For instance, IoT can shift renewable energy project execution to a very advanced level via the deployment of smart sensors and intelligent meters. Such an adoption is well-tested by others like Shell, “the giant of the energy sector”, which is heavily utilizing IoT for robotic inspection and land surveys (Yadoshchuk, 2024).

7.3. Cloud Computing

Public cloud PaaS market grew up by 37% in 2020 recording \$305 billion in 2021 (Anon., 2023). It forecasts a 16% growth and \$690 billion by end of 2024 (Smith, et al., 2024). This IE4 arm enabled alfanar, among 70% of cloud-adapting firms, to overcome challenges related to data consolidation and ERP integration across its subsidiaries. By adopting hyper cloud solutions, the company makes significant cost savings in the IT license management, and further, it enhanced alfanar’s data security and transferred a considerable amount of the data risk to Microsoft which invests \$1 billion annually in protecting Azure, which treats 7 trillion cyber threats on a daily basis (Anon., 2023)

7.4. Cybersecurity

As manufacturers expand their digital infrastructures, cybersecurity becomes crucial. alfanar addresses potential security risks including data breaches and ransomware attacks, through robust security protocols, employee training, and advanced threat detection tools. It is utilizing SAP GRC to maintain its strong RBAC system while maintaining a comprehensive DRP.

8. Impacts of IE4 Mega Trends on alfanar Group

Table 1 below summarizes the potential results of both embracing as well as late adoption of the analyzed trends covering productivity, finance, process, and customer support as addressed for the electrical industry, whereas the following paragraphs will elaborate, with more details, on alfanar’s environment.

Mega Trend	Result of Embracing it	Result of Late Adaptation
AI & ML	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced Service Delivery Data-Driven Decisions FTE Cost Saving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential Operational Inefficiencies Potential Lose of Market Shares Increased Internal Communication
IoT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Machinery Optimization Quality Improvement Reduced Downtime 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential Scarp Volume Lack of JIT Capabilities Lack of Plants' Connectivity
Cloud Computing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scalability of IT Application Maximized Flexibility Enhanced Data Accessibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silos and Lack of Consolidation Higher IT infrastructure Cost ERP Manual Updates
Cybersecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory Compliance Higher Trust Maintained Reputation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential Operational Disruptions Potential Data Breaches Potential Fines & Penalties

Table 1: IE4 Mega Trends Impact Summary
 Source: Author Findings

8.1. Accenture Distribution Module

According to Accenture distribution module (Figure 4) which illustrates the disruption possibility through its four quadrants (Durability, Viability, Vulnerability and Volatility) almost all alfanar Group’s sectors face high disruption now and in future (Figure 5).

THE FOUR PERIODS OF INDUSTRY DISRUPTION

Figure 4: Accenture Distribution Module
Source: techwireasia.com

Figure 5: alfanar Group position in Accenture Distribution Module
Source: Author Findings

8.2. PESTEL Analysis

PESTEL analysis illustrates the possible impact and implications of the above-mentioned mega trends on alfanar along its six pillars.

8.2.1. Political Factors

A

Policies issued by the Saudi Data and Artificial Intelligence Authority (SDAIA) for technology adoption, under Saudi Vision 2030, significantly facilitate the implementation of AI and ML at alfanar. These policies promote innovation and digital transformation, aligning with the national strategy. Additionally, compliance with international relevant guidelines ensures responsible practices of AI, cloud computing and cybersecurity, particularly in HR and contract management. This dual focus on national and international standards helps alfanar leverage IE4 technologies effectively while adhering to ethical guidelines and regulatory requirements, fostering trust, and securing the reputation.

B

Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 includes significant investments in smart infrastructure and IoT technologies, facilitating the import of semi-finished or finished IoT instruments and devices for manufacturers. This strategic focus enhances firms' capabilities in managing big data through IoT applications. However, compliance with data security and privacy regulations is essential to ensure a successful transformation. Adhering to these standards not only meets regulatory requirements but also builds trust with stakeholders and customers, ensuring the secure and efficient deployment of IE4 technologies across the operations.

C

Both Saudi Arabia's and European data hosting and transfer laws significantly impact alfanar's cloud initiatives. In Saudi Arabia, SDAIA laws require that certain types of data must be stored within the country, while the European Union's GDPR imposes strict regulations on data protection and cross-border data transfers. These regulations necessitate a multi-instance approach to cloud architecture to ensure compliance across different areas.

D

Implementing a comprehensive global ERP data architecture that enables product lifecycle tracking across alfanar Group subsidiaries is essential. This approach ensures that data is managed and stored in compliance with local regulations, thereby mitigating legal risks and enhancing operational efficiency.

E

The Saudi Arabia's National Cybersecurity Authority (NCA) mandates strict cybersecurity measures for organizations to protect critical infrastructure and sensitive data. These regulations require companies like alfanar to implement robust cybersecurity frameworks, conduct regular security audits, and ensure the protection of data against cyber threats. Compliance with these regulations is not just a legal requirement but also a strategic necessity to avoid penalties and to protect the reputation. Additionally, these regulations align with international cybersecurity standards, enhancing the overall competitiveness level of firms operating across the global market.

Figure 6: Political Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.2.2. Economical Factors

F

AI and ML implementation drives significant cost savings through the automation of shared services and corporate supply chain. AI and ML may enable alfanar to quickly leverage corporate practices and group standards across its subsidiaries, and accordingly enhance its operational efficiency. This contributes to overall economic growth and competitiveness in the global market.

G

Early adoption of IoT can lead to substantial cost reductions and enhance competitiveness in manufacturing standard electrical products like switches, sockets, breakers, and wires. Competing with industry giants such as GE, Siemens, Shell, Schneider, and Mitsubishi, alfanar can leverage IoT to scale up its market share, improve efficiency, and boost productivity. This also contributes to economic growth, and further, it can position alfanar as a major player in the global market not only in the GCC market.

H

Adopting cloud computing can significantly enhance alfanar's financial performance by reducing the need for physical infrastructure and maintenance, resulting in substantial cost savings. However, fluctuating economic conditions may impact IT budgets, influencing the extent and speed of cloud adoption. By leveraging cloud technologies, alfanar can optimize operational efficiency and remain agile in responding to market changes, supporting sustained economic growth.

*Figure 7: Economical Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings*

8.2.3. Social Factors

I

AI transformation addresses potential job displacement concerns among all employee levels. An initiative-taking for a comprehensive reskilling approach helps mitigate such a social impact of transformation, ensuring a skilled and adaptable workforce. Additionally, rising expectations for AI-driven communication and services influence alfanar's reputation and attractiveness to Gen Z talent. By investing in AI and prioritizing employee development along with leveraging a digital organizational culture, alfanar shall be able to enhance its social responsibility, strengthens its market position, and attracts high-talent candidates.

J

The integration of IoT and advanced automation at alfanar necessitates a skillful and highly-paid workforce which addresses salary gaps among white-collar workers, especially the engineering job holders. However, a comprehensive reskilling programs help employees get equipped to manage and effectively use modern technologies, mitigating social impacts and fostering a culture of continuous learning.

K

The increasing use of social media significantly impacts alfanar's transformation as far as it highly influences consumer perceptions and brand reputation. Engaging effectively on social media platforms can enhance alfanar's visibility, foster customer loyalty, and attract top talent. However, it also requires the company to manage its digital presence carefully, addressing any negative feedback promptly to maintain a positive image. Moreover, the shift towards digital communication necessitates training employees in social media and digital marketing best practices, ensuring they are capable to optimize these platforms for the best level of customers and stakeholders engagement, thereby reinforcing alfanar's commitment to innovation and customer satisfaction.

*Figure 8: Social Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings*

8.2.4. Technological Factors

L Leveraging AI and ML technologies requires effective data analysis, making big data solutions integral to alfanar's AI initiatives. This step-by-step integration ensures that data is harnessed efficiently, enabling predictive and prescriptive analytics. Consequently, these technologies can enhance product development cycles and improve manufacturing, maintenance and services efficiency, which position alfanar within a harder energy-sector competition.

M IoT fosters technological advancements that drive disruptive innovation in both power solutions and electrical products. For example, SCADA solutions are transitioning from wire-based to IoT sensor-based control systems. As global manufacturers build smart factories requiring the effective integration of IoT devices and industrial systems, alfanar should leverage its technological expertise commercially, starting at its industrial plants, and then, expanding towards global market. This approach is like GE's strategy applied through its consultancy arm, GE Digital. Such initiatives will help alfanar continue to lead in technological innovation and smart manufacturing, thereby enhancing its competitive edge in the market.

N Cloud computing drives significant technological advancements by enhancing data storage, processing, and accessibility. The shift to cloud infrastructure enables real-time data analytics, improving decision-making processes and operational efficiency. Without adopting cloud technologies, alfanar can hardly scale its IT resources. Further, manufacturers investing in cloud computing dynamically reduce physical infrastructure costs and increase agility in deploying new applications and services which add more challenges in front of late technology-adapting firms, thus, it is a must for alfanar Group to continue improving its cloud computing across all its subsidiaries.

Figure 9: Technological Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation

Source: Author Findings

8.2.5. Environmental Factors

O AI and ML technologies help, through advanced R&D, optimizing production BoM (Bill of Materials) calculations, reducing metal and plastic consumption in the energy manufacturing processes which contributes to sustainability goals. Furthermore, AI can aid in developing comprehensive guidance and procedures to maintain a healthy environment within factories and project sites. By leveraging AI for efficient resource utilization and environmental management, alfanar enhances its sustainability efforts, minimizes waste, and promotes a safer and healthier workplace, reinforcing its commitment to environmental stewardship and innovation

P Using its renewable energy solutions, companies in the power sector started optimizing energy usage in their own manufacturing and building operations, contributing to sustainability goals. IoT devices helped in monitoring the environmental conditions within industrial plants, providing real-time alerts on deviations from localized standards. This enhances compliance with environmental regulations and promotes sustainable practices. By leveraging IoT for energy management and environmental monitoring, alfanar not only improves operational efficiency but also reinforces its commitment to environmental responsibility and sustainable development.

Q Adopting cloud computing technologies allows to optimize data storage and processing capabilities, significantly reducing the need for physical infrastructure and lowering energy consumption. This helps in minimizing the carbon footprint associated with maintaining large on-premises data centers.

Figure 10: Environmental Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation

Source: Author Findings

8.2.6. Legal Factors

R	Protecting AI and ML innovations through intellectual property rights, patents, and trademarks is crucial for maintaining a competitive edge. Additionally, ensuring adherence to legal standards related to AI ethics, data privacy (such as GDPR and Saudi Arabia's PDPL), and usage rights is essential for responsible implementation. This compliance mitigates legal risks and obligations, fostering trust and ensuring the ethical deployment of AI technologies. By securing its AI innovations and complying with relevant regulations, alfanar can strengthen its market position and reputation as a leader in responsible AI usage.
S	alfanar is legally obligated to produce safe products and to adhere to its warranties. IoT technology assists in deploying systems that alert for issues such as power cable plastic insulation defects and non-conformity of electrical switches. By implementing these IoT systems, alfanar ensures compliance with safety standards and regulatory requirements, thereby minimizing legal risks and enhancing product reliability. Such a proactive approach not only meets legal requirements but also reinforces consumer trust and upholds the Group's reputation for high-quality and safe electrical products.
T	Adopting cloud computing technologies necessitates compliance with various data protection and privacy laws, both locally and internationally. Saudi Arabia's data sovereignty regulations and the European Union's GDPR impose strict requirements on how data is stored, processed, and transferred. Ensuring compliance with these regulations is critical to avoid fines and ensure the integrity and security of sensitive information impacting the reputation. alfanar must continue implementing robust data governance frameworks while adhering to legal standards to mitigate legal risks and maintain its image as a responsible and compliant branded firm.

Figure 11: Legal Factors Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.3. Five Forces Analysis

Five Forces analysis illustrates the possible impact and implications of the trends in-scope of this report on alfanar from five different perspectives, listed below.

8.3.1. Threat of New Entrants

A	The adoption of AI and IoT technologies can lower barriers to both entry and expansion by enabling new competitors to quickly develop innovative solutions and disrupt the market. However, alfanar's established reputation and expertise in these technologies provide a significant competitive edge.
B	The capital investment required for robust IoT, and advanced cloud infrastructure can stop or delay new entrants. alfanar's strategic partnerships and existing infrastructure in IT providers enhance its competitive positioning.
C	High barriers due to the need for advanced skills and technology to ensure robust cybersecurity can limit new entrants. alfanar's investment in state-of-the-art cybersecurity measures secures its market position to a satisfying level.

Figure 12: Threat of New Entrants Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.3.2. Bargaining Power of Suppliers

D

Suppliers of AI and IoT components and similar technologies hold high power due to the specialized nature of these products. alfanar's long-term relationships with key technology suppliers and its strategic sourcing strategies help mitigate this power.

E

Major cloud service providers like AWS, Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud hold significant bargaining power. However, alfanar's multi-source strategy can reduce dependency on a single supplier, balancing the power dynamics.

F

The quickly-improving nature of cybersecurity tools and services along with the continuously-changing threats, gives the cybersecurity service providers additional commercial power, thus, alfanar's investment in developing in-house cybersecurity capabilities can reduce reliance on external consultancies.

Figure 13: Bargaining Power of Suppliers Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.3.3. Bargaining Power of Buyers

G

Buyers, both corporates and individuals, increasingly demand advanced solutions that enhance operational efficiency and productivity. alfanar's continuous innovation (smart meters for instance) along with the high-quality offerings strengthen its bargaining position with buyers.

H

Buyers are extremely sensitive to cybersecurity due to the potential risks and impacts of breaches. alfanar's robust cybersecurity solutions and commitment for reliability give it a strong bargaining position with governmental sector, private construction contractors and individual constructors.

Figure 14: Bargaining Power of Buyers Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.3.4. Threat of Substitutes

I

The rapid advancement of renewable energy addresses constantly-emerging alternatives. However, alfanar's comprehensive and integrated IoT systems heavily applied on its renewable energy business sector reduce that threat of substitutes.

J

Traditional on-premises infrastructure in the small subsidiaries can be a cost-effective substitute for cloud services. alfanar's focus on demonstrating the cost-efficiency by leveraging scalability and flexibility of cloud solutions which helps mitigate this threat.

K

Out-sourced cybersecurity services can function as a substitute for local small competitors, but their ineffectiveness compared to advanced security solutions makes them less threatening. alfanar's in-house cybersecurity team commitment to cutting-edge practices reduces this specific threat from substitutes.

Figure 15: Threat of Substitutes Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

8.3.5. Industry Rivalry

L	The energy market is highly competitive with major players like GE, Siemens, Shell, Schneider, and Mitsubishi. alfanar’s continuous innovation on AI and IoT, strategic partnerships, and comprehensive solutions help maintain a competitive edge.
M	The cloud computing market is dominated by few large players, leading to intense competition among them. alfanar’s negotiation ability enables unique bidding power locally whereas integrating the cloud services of its global operations helps it stand out with both product lifecycle and supply chain management.
N	The cybersecurity market requires dynamic decision making due to the constant evolution of threats and solutions. alfanar’s approach to advanced cybersecurity enhances its competitive position in this regard.

Figure 16: Industry Rivalry Impacting alfanar Transformation
Source: Author Findings

9. Challenges with IE4 Mega Trends

9.1. Challenges of AI

AI addresses challenging risks across various aspects; specially with accuracy, cybersecurity, intellectual property, and regularity compliance (Figure 17). Deloitte reported that 20% of high-AI-performance companies challenge the lack of skilled talents as well as the difficulty of scalable adaptation (Anon., 2023).

Figure 17: Gen AI Risks
Source: McKinsey & Company

Only 56% of companies confirmed that they have achieved a responsible AI Implementation whereas 37% of them report delays in their transformation initiatives because of the limited expertise (Stackpole, 2022).

9.2. Challenges of IoT

IoT requires manufacturers integrating complex and expensive hardware, communication, cloud services and software application (Figure 18) which require, in turn, rare skill-set; especially when facing operational incidents.

Figure 18: Layers of an IoT solution
Source: euristiq.com

IoT Capital investments shall also follow rapidly evolving technology which puts the whole asset value at considerable risk unless hard depreciation is applied. IoT investments go for millions of dollars whereas a single point device may cost \$10,000 (Rupareliya, 2023). Yet, about 25% of IoT investing companies still need to put considerable efforts to overcome various serious challenges (Table 2).

Challenge	Percentage
Complexity/technical challenges	38%
Lack of budget/skilled staff	29%
Limited IoT expertise	29%
Failure to identify the right IoT solution	28%
Security issues	19%

Table 2: Percentage of IoT investing companies vs. top challenges
 Source: Microsoft IoT Signals survey

Additionally, IoT project management addresses a high potential risk of failure resulted from five main reasons (Figure 19) which can't be mitigated without investing in higher expertise, continuous R&D, extensive marketing analysis, and professional consultancies (Anon., 2022).

Figure 19: Percent of IoT failure reasons
 Source: expanice.com

9.3. Challenges of Cloud Computing

Unlike technology leaders, whose cloud investment is designed to generate revenue from consumers, there is not a precise ROI of cloud computing for energy manufacturers since most of their products and services are not targeting individuals directly.

Companies, utilizing cloud computing like alfanar, face different challenges like, but not limited to network and applications' security, access management and license cost (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Percent of Companies vs. cloud computing challenges
Source: KPMG.com

9.4. Challenges of Cybersecurity

Table 3, below, shows the most important challenges of embracing cybersecurity:

Challenge Keywords	Description of challenge
Rapid Threat Changes	The cybersecurity landscape is rapidly evolving. Threats are becoming more sophisticated and diverse. This includes cybercriminals, hacktivists, and nation-state actors.
Lack of Skilled Professionals	There is a significant shortage of skilled cybersecurity professionals. This gap makes it difficult to build and maintain robust cybersecurity teams and increases competition for highly paid talent.
Legal Compliance	Regulations governing cybersecurity is becoming increasingly complex many local, national, and international regulations related to data protection, privacy, and cybersecurity issued whereas compliance, of globally-operating companies requires significant resources and continuous monitoring to assure full adherence
Cost of implementation	Allocating insufficient funds to cybersecurity limit the ability to invest in advanced security tools.

*Table 3: alfanar Group Challenges of Cybersecurity
Source: Author Findings*

10. Conclusion

alfanar Group's DIGI-Fit future is driven by the strategic adoption IE4. The analysis of megatrends highlights technological advancements, offers cost efficiencies and scalable solutions, essential for meeting fluctuating and dynamically-changing market demands. IE4 technologies collectively enhance alfanar Group's competitiveness, drive innovation in electrical product development, and support shared services initiatives. The integration of AI and IoT addresses potential cost saving and higher efficiency. Cloud computing further supports operational agility and environmental connectivity. However, challenges persist, including the need for full compliance with data protection regulations and managing the complexity of integrating these advanced technologies. The bargaining power of global technology suppliers, coupled with the threat of substitutes and industry rivalry, requires alfanar Group to maintain a strategic focus on R&D and workforce development. By leveraging its technological expertise and addressing these challenges proactively, alfanar Group is well-positioned to achieve sustainable growth, operational excellence, and a robust competitive edge in the global market.

In conclusion, alfanar Group stands at a pivotal point where embracing digital transformation can highly influence its future success and drive its business growth.

11. Recommendations

Based on this report, Table 4, here below, addresses six recommendations for alfanar Group to lift the IE4 Adoption towards a DIGI-Fit future:

Scope	Action needed
Digital Strategy	Create a clear roadmap for integrating AI, IoT, cloud computing, and cybersecurity, aligning with alfanar Group's long-term goals, industry trends, and KSA vision 2030.
Workforce Training	Implement extensive training programs to upskill alfanar employees, bridge skill gaps towards IE4, and ensure effective implementation.
Data Management	Establish a robust data governance framework to improve data quality and leverage AI and ML for advanced analytics and decision-making.
Cross-Functional Collaboration	Promote collaboration across IT, Project Management, Manufacturing, HR, Finance, Facility Management, and Procurement to ensure integrated and seamless adoption of new technologies.
Customer-Centric Innovation	Develop AI-driven and IoT-enabled products and services that meet evolving customer needs, enhancing customer satisfaction and strengthen alfanar competitive advantages.
Regulatory Compliance	Ensure compliance with local and international regulations related to data privacy, cybersecurity, and technology adoption to avoid legal issues and build trust with all stakeholders.

*Table 4: Recommendations for alfanar Group to Lift the IE4 Adoption
Source: Author Findings*

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